

Extractive spectrophotometric determination of tungsten(VI) as its 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran complex

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Abstract : An extractive spectrophotometric method is developed for the trace determination of tungsten in acidic medium. A light yellow (1 : 2) complex of tungsten(VI) is formed with 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HL) in perchloric acid medium. The coloured species is quantitatively extracted into dichloromethane and absorbance is measured at 405–412 nm. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0–3.1 $\mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$, with a molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $4.69 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0039 \mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively at 410 nm. The method is free from the interference of Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Nb, Ta, Mo, U, Zr, Th, Ce, Re and platinum metals. The proposed system handles satisfactorily the analysis of several samples of varying complexity.

Keywords : Tungsten(VI), substituted benzopyran, dichloromethane.

The existing methods of spectrophotometric determination of tungsten using binary complexes are generally time consuming, less sensitive, non selective and thus have limited applications due to more complexity of procedures¹. In view of the above observations, it is considered of interest to study the complex formation reaction of tungsten(VI) with 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HL) which not only gives a more rapid and highly reproducible method but also provides a highly selective and sensitive extractive spectrophotometric determination of tungsten in trace amounts.

Results and discussion

HL reacts with tungsten(VI) in perchloric acid medium to give a light yellow coloured stable complex extractable into dichloromethane quantitatively. In other acids such as HCl, H₂SO₄, CH₃COOH and H₃PO₄, lower value of absorbance is observed in the same order. The absorption spectrum of the light yellow complex in dichloromethane indicates that the maximum lies in the range 405–412 nm where the reagent blank has small absorbance (Fig. 1). The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance are : 0.12–0.26 M HClO₄ and 0.9–2.5 ml of 0.002 M HL solution in ethanol for 0–31 μg of W^{VI} per 10 ml aqueous solution, equilibrating with 10 ml of dichloromethane once during 5–300 s (Table 1). Organic solvents dichloromethane,

chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane, benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, isobutyl methyl ketone, isopentyl alcohol, isopentyl acetate, ethyl acetate and cyclohexane extract the metal complex in the decreasing order. In dichloromethane, the absorbance remains unchanged for more than 6 h. Hence, it is preferred as an extractant for the metal complex. A single equilibration with 10 ml of dichloromethane quantitatively transfers the W^{VI}-HL complex to the organic phase.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of W^{VI}-HL complex in dichloromethane : (A) 2.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of tungsten(VI) measured against reagent blank, (B) reagent blank measured against pure dichloromethane.

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of W^{VI} -HL complex

$HClO_4$ (M) ^a	0.00	0.02	0.08	0.10	0.12-0.26	0.28	0.30
Absorbance	0.385	0.420	0.480	0.495	0.510	0.490	0.470
HL ^b (0.002 M in ethanol, ml)	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.8	0.9-2.5	3.0	
Absorbance	0.075	0.230	0.370	0.490	0.510	0.470	
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	2	5-300				
Absorbance	0.020	0.350	0.510				

^a $W^{VI} = 20 \mu\text{g}$, $HClO_4 = \text{variable}$, $0.002 \text{ M HL} = 1 \text{ ml}$, equilibration time = 30 s, solvent = dichloromethane, absorbance measured at 410 nm against reagent blank. ^b $W^{VI} = 20 \mu\text{g}$, $HClO_4 = 0.2 \text{ M}$, other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in HL concentration, also $b = 3\text{-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran}$. ^c $0.002 \text{ M HL in ethanol} = 1 \text{ ml}$, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

Beer's law holds well in the concentration range 0–3.1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of tungsten. However, the optimum range of determination as evaluated from Ringbom plot is 0.52 to 3.02 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of tungsten. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex are $4.69 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0039 \mu\text{g W}^{VI} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively at 410 nm. The tungsten(VI) to HL ratio in the extracted species has been determined as 1 : 2 by the Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper for a two phase system² and also by the mole ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions :

Under the optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, nitrate, acetate, thiourea and carbonate (100 mg each); sulphite, nitrite, thiocyanate and dithionite (70 mg each); phosphate, ascorbic acid, EDTA 'disodium salt', hydrazine sulphate and sulfosalicylic acid (50 mg each); tartrate (10 mg); citrate (5 mg); fluoride (1 mg); H_2O_2 (6%, w/v) and glycerol (0.1 ml each) did not affect the determination. However, oxalate interfered seriously even in traces. Among the cations, Co^{II} , Ca^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Hg^{II} , Mg^{II} , Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} , As^V and Ag^I (10 mg each); Al^{III} (8 mg); Se^{IV} , Cr^{VI} and Cd^{II} (5 mg each); Cr^{III} (4 mg); Be^{II} and Ce^{IV} (3 mg each); U^{VI} (2 mg); Bi^{III} and Os^{VIII} (1 mg each); Cu^{II} (0.9 mg); Th^{IV} (0.5 mg); Pt^{II} (0.4 mg); Nb^V (0.3 mg); Zr^{IV} , Ru^{III} , Re^{VII} , Au^{III} , Ta^V , Pd^{II} and Ir^{III} (0.1 mg each) and V^V (0.08 mg) caused $\leq 1\%$ error. Sn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ti^{IV} and Mo^{VI} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under modifications of the procedure.

The wide applicability of the method is tested by the analysis of several synthetic (some of them analogous to minargent, platinoid, W-alloy, heat resistant steel, high speed steel and stellite No. 2) and reverberatory flue dust samples with satisfactory results (Table 2). The proposed spectrophotometric method is simple, rapid, sensitive and is free from the interferences of a large number (38) of

metal ions including platinum metals and also elements like Ti, V, Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Mo, U, Zr, Nb and Re. The high reproducibility of the method is tested by performing ten sets of experiments while keeping the same ($2 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) amount of W^{VI} each time. The relative standard deviation of the method is 0.35%. The proposed method is comparable with the existing methods^{1,3} particularly in respect of sensitivity, selectivity and rapidity.

Experimental

UV-VIS (Shimadzu-140-02) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cells was used for routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies. The standard stock solutions of tungsten(VI) and other ions were prepared as reported earlier⁴. 2 M perchloric acid was prepared by suitable dilution of the 11.6 M acid. 3-Hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HL), (m.p. 190–192 °C) was synthesized by the literature method⁵ and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.002 M solution. The structure of HL is

Dichloromethane (RANKEM) was used as such.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing tungsten solution with solution of other metal ions in suitable proportions as shown in Table 2. The dust sample (0.1 g) from copper manufacture, containing no tungsten, was mixed with a known content of tungsten (1 mg) and brought into solution as reported⁴. The leach was treated with 1 g

Note

Table 2. Analysis of various samples with the studied method; in parenthese amount of the metal ions, mg

Matrix	Sample Composition	W added µg	W found*, µg	
			Proposed method	HTC method
Cu (0.2), Ni (0.2), Pb (0.12)**		20.0	19.88 ± 0.8	20.14
Cu (0.6), Zn (0.25), Ni (0.15)**		10.0	9.81 ± 1.3	10.00
Cu (0.15), Zn (0.08), Al (0.12)**		15.0	15.19 ± 0.9	15.24
Fe (0.15), Cr (0.03), Co (0.03), Mn (0.01), Ni (0.01)** ^a		20.0	20.19 ± 0.7	20.29
Fe (0.15), Cr (0.004), V (0.002)** ^a		25.0	25.13 ± 0.9	24.86
Co (0.12), Cr (0.08), Fe (0.02)** ^a		20.0	19.93 ± 0.4	20.00
Ce (1), Sn (0.05), As (1) ^b		10.0	10.12 ± 1.6	9.71
Mo (0.01), Fe (0.5), Ba (1) ^c		15.0	15.13 ± 1.1	14.86
Cu (0.5), Ti (0.01), Pb (5) ^d		20.0	19.73 ± 0.4	20.00
U (1), Ir (0.01), Cr ^{VI} (1), Mg (1)		25.0	25.13 ± 0.3	25.09
Pt (0.1), Pd (0.05), Mn (5), Sr (1)		30.0	29.80 ± 0.8	30.60
Nb (0.1), Cr ^{III} (1), Se (1)		10.0	10.12 ± 0.8	10.14
Reverberatory flue dust (100)		10.0	10.19 ± 1.3	10.29
		20.0	20.26 ± 0.8	19.71

*Average of triplicate analyses Mean ± %RSD.

**Sample Nos. 1–6 correspond to minargent, platinoid, W-alloy, heat resistant steel, high speed steel and stellite No. 2, respectively.

^aIn presence of 50 mg ascorbic acid.

^bIn presence of 1 mg sodium fluoride.

^cIn presence of 0.1 ml of 6% (w/v) H₂O₂ and 50 mg ascorbic acid.

^dIn presence of 50 mg sodium phosphate.

sodium potassium tartrate, neutralized with concentrated HClO₄ and adjusted to 2 M acidity in 100 ml final volume. Aliquots (1 and 2 ml) were taken for the determination of tungsten by the proposed method.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution containing ≤ 31 µg tungsten(VI) were added 1 ml of 2 M HClO₄, 1 ml of 0.002 M HL reagent and enough deionized water to raise the aqueous volume to 10 ml in a 100 ml separatory funnel. The contents were then equilibrated with 10 ml of dichloromethane, once for 30 s and the layers were allowed to separate. The light yellow coloured organic phase was then passed through Whatman filter paper (No. 41, pretreated with dichloromethane) to remove water droplets. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 410 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank. The amount of tungsten was determined from the calibration curve obtained as per the proposed procedure.

Modifications for the samples containing Sn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ti^{IV} and Mo^{VI}: For 0.1 mg of Sn^{II}, 1 mg sodium fluoride; 2 mg of Fe^{III}, 50 mg ascorbic acid; 0.1 mg of Ti^{IV}, 50 mg sodium phosphate and for 0.05 mg of Mo^{VI}, 0.1 ml of 6% (w/v) H₂O₂ were added as masking agents prior to the addition of HL in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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